

A PARAMĀRA SCULPTURE IN THE BRITISH MUSEUM : VĀGDEVĪ OR YAKSHĪ AMBIKĀ ?

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Around the year 1880 the British Museum in London acquired one inscribed stone sculpture of a goddess that had probably been found from the ruins of Dhar, ancient Dhārā, in Malwa¹ (Fig. 1). The sculpture was described and identified by O. C. Gangoly in a paper in which he also included K. N. Dikshit's reading of the four line inscription on the pedestal.² The writing, as indeed the image as a whole, is considerably damaged, still Dikshit could decipher parts of it : the name of a king Bhoja; a reference to his capital city; Saṃvat 1091 or 1034-35 A. D. as the date of the carving ; and the name of the goddess Vāgdevī. Bhoja is, of course, the Paramāra king who ruled with Dhārā as his capital between circa 1005 and 1055 A. D. An ambitious king who fought numerous wars during his long reign, Bhoja is remembered more for his love of learning and his own scholarship; legend ascribes to him the authorship of eightyfour works on grammar, rhetorics, architecture and other subjects, and the establishment in his capital of a college, the Sarasvatīśādhana, where Bhoja himself presided over learned discussion³.

We can well imagine the joy of Dikshit and Gangoly at their exciting decipherment of the inscription; ever since the publication of the paper the British Museum sculpture has been considered as an image of Vāgdevī-Sarasvatī --in fact, the very image installed in his college by Bhoja himself. Bhoja having been regarded in the Indian tradition as perhaps the example of a blend of king and scholar, the man of action who is at the same time the man of erudition, this stately sculpture has acquired a romantic aura that is all its own.

Later scholars have also tried to read the record on the image, but the full text has never been satisfactorily explained; the original assumptions that the word *Vāgdevī* refers to this particular image, and that the goddess was installed by Bhoja, have nowhere been substantiated. If we are not carried away by the occurrence together of the names of Bhoja and Vāgdevī-Sarasvatī in the inscription which is as yet only imperfectly understood, there is little in the *iconography* of the figure to support an identification with Sarasvatī; on the contrary, even in the present mutilated

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condition of the figure, every surviving feature reveals that the sculpture represents the Jaina goddess Ambikā, the Yakshī or Śāsanadevatā of the twenty-second Tīrthānkra Neminātha. In this paper I shall first describe the principal sculpture and the companion figures and discuss the newly proposed identification with Ambikā ; after this a fresh interpretation, of the pedestal inscription which corroborates the identification, will be suggested.

The sculpture is of grey stone and measures 1.297 x 507 m (4'3" x 1' 8½"). The goddess, standing in *ābhāṅga* against a plain background, had four arms, but three of them are broken and their attributes destroyed. The back right hand, the only one preserved, holds an *aṅkuṣa* or elephant goad as may be seen in the detail photograph published here (Fig. 2). The lower half of its shaft is broken, a trace of its bottom end being preserved against the elbow, but the upper part is intact and carries three ornamental moldings. In contrast to the ample proportions of the shaft itself, the hook of the goad is rather slender. The left rear arm of the goddess as well as the attribute of the hand are also destroyed, but we can discern the manneristic bend of the fingers gripping the stem or tip of some object. The hair of the goddess is coiled in a large bun over her right shoulder and over this she wears a *karāṇḍa* crown; she wears the usual adornments, and a fine lower garment (*charaṇikā*) reaching down to her ankles.

The base of the sculpture has two offsets corresponding to the *Pañcharatha* type of pedestal. Four figures flank the goddess, she herself towering over their small-proportioned forms. On her left (Fig. 3) is her mount, a capering lion. A plump boy rides animal, supporting a large mango fruit on the palm of his left hand while he holds up his right arm in adoration⁴. He has a round face and has close-cropped hair and wears some ornaments.

On the right of the goddess are a child and a man (Fig. 4). This child is younger in age than the lion-rider; from his bonny frame and short stature we may judge that he is a mere toddler. His hair is short and curly, he wears adornments that are similar to his brother's, and a loin-cloth.⁵ On the palm of his right hand he supports a large and nearly round fruit with a pointed tip; perhaps this is not another mango but a *mātuluṅga* or *bījapūraka* : however, it has a smooth skin. The left arm was probably held up in adoration but is broken.

Behind this child stands a full grown man, his position in the background, on the innermost step of the pedestal, suggesting that he has only a secondary role in the story. He has a beard; he wears a *karāṇḍa* crown and other ornaments including a *chhannavīra*. His right hand rests along

the side of his body while the left holds one end of a damaged rod, the other end resting against the waist.⁶ In the top left corner of the stele a flying celestial approaches the goddess with a garland, his counterpart in the opposite corner being totally obliterated.

Every single feature of the sculpture corresponds to the Jaina yakshī Ambikā as known from carvings from all over the country. Her iconography may be described in brief: When two-armed, she usually holds a bunch of mangoes in her right hand and supports her younger child on her waist if she is standing and on her lap if seated.⁷ Or both the boys may stand on either side of their mother while she lovingly places her hand over the head of one.⁸

Ambikā may also have four arms; such images, in which Ambikā is conceived of as a goddess rather than as a yakshī or śāsanadevatā, begin to occur from the tenth-eleventh century, and are relatively fewer. In this form the two additional hands may hold a goad and a noose, or the mango bunch is repeated in both these extra hands.⁹

The lion is Ambikā's mount; in sculptures he either serves as her seat or occurs by the side of the standing goddess. In the latter case, the older child often straddling the frolicking lion as in our own sculpture, while the smaller child reaches up to snatch a mango.¹⁰

In addition to the above, a bough of a mango tree nearly always forms a canopy over her figure. The whole composition being crowned by the Tirthaṅkara Neminātha, the patron Jīna of the yakshī.

An image of Ambikā, then, is recognisable by a mango bunch, a citron, a goad and a noose in her hands, mango branches crowning her head, a toddler child and an older boy gamboling with a lion. It should not, therefore, be too difficult to recognise Ambikā in the British Museum sculpture even though three of her arms are broken. True, the mango boughs and the surmounting Tirthaṅkara are absent, but we can cite a few other images of Ambikā where one or both of them are similarly lacking; for example a stone sculpture of the sixth century from Shahabad district in Bihar and some bronzes of Akota¹¹ are without the foliage. The same sculpture from Shahabad, another from Hinglajgarh in Madhya Pradesh, and an eastern Indian bronze in the National Museum are devoid of the Tirthaṅkara figure.¹²

As to the current identification with Sarasvatī, a comparison with some genuine images of Sarasvatī, both Brahmanical and Jaina, from central and western India, fails to bear it out.¹³ The objects in the hands

of Sarasvatī are evocative of ascetic virtue, spiritual learning, music, the chanting of hymns, immortality. A prominent type of the Brahmanical Sarasvatī's image, based on a brief description in the *Agnipurāṇa* 50.16, has a *vīṇā*, a rosary and a manuscript, the *vīṇā* occupying two hands.¹⁴ A variant type adds a fourth attribute, either a *kamaṇḍalu*-pitcher (*Vishṇudharmottara-purāṇa* III. 64.2—suggestive of the original riverine being of the goddess) or a nectar jar (*Śāradātilaka*, VIIIth Paṭala: Bhattasali, table at p. 189). But in neither of these forms does the elephant goad occur. The Jaina conception of Sarasvatī is similar to the Brahmanical, the objects in her hands being a rosary, lotus, manuscript and jar (as may be seen in the two identical images from Pallu¹⁵), but here too the goad is absent.

Two features of our sculpture might appear to support the current identification with Sarasvatī, namely the goad and the lion mount. The goad indeed is given to Sarasvatī in Deccani and south Indian images¹⁶ (perhaps under the influence of Gaṇeśa's iconography). But nowhere in northern India does the goad figure in Sarasvatī's images, and therefore our sculpture which follows the Mālava style cannot be considered as being of Sarasvatī.

The mount of Sarasvatī is the goose (*hamsa*); in south India and the Deccan it is sometimes the peacock and in Bengal the ram¹⁷. Haridas Bhattacharyya first suggested that the lion can also be the mount of Sarasvatī, and his suggestion has been dutifully repeated by all later scholars who wrote on this goddess of learning. True that author cited texts in which Sarasvatī, there synonymous with Durgā, is Śiva's Śakti; her characteristics are a snow-white complexion, three eyes, the crescent moon, tiger skin garment, serpent ornaments, a trident in her hand and a lion mount (Bhattacharyya, p. 49). But the British Museum image has nothing in common with this synthetic form which has so many attributes of Durgā. Again, Bhattacharyya's assertion loses all its force when we look up the only sculpture cited by him as evidence, namely an early image in the Mathura Museum, for the goddess there has no mount at all, but sits directly on a plain pedestal¹⁸. We must, therefore, give up the belief that the lion can occur as the mount of Vāgdevī-Sarasvatī, and the sculpture in London cannot on this account be identified with the goddess of learning.

It has already been suggested above that the current identification of our sculpture is based solely on the wrong premise that the word *Vāgdevī* in the epigraph refers to the present sculpture itself. We have also considered and (hopefully) disproved the arguments that might be raised, *a posteriori*, in its favour. On making a fresh study of the inscription, we are

pleasantly surprised that it corroborates our own conclusion that the image represents the Jaina yakshī Ambikā, as we shall presently see.

The inscription (Fig. 5) is engraved on the central offset of the pedestal and consists of four lines ; it contains one verse in the *śārdūlavikrīḍita* metre followed by a line in prose giving the name of the sculptor etc. and the date Samvat 1091 corresponding to 1034-35 A. D. An oblique fissure in the stone has destroyed one or more characters in the first three lines and has divided the record into two unequal parts, the writing on the left of the fissure being relatively better preserved compared to that on the right. Perhaps this part of the pedestal had been more exposed to weathering.

Several enthusiastic students of Malwa's art and culture have tried to decipher the inscription since its first publication in *Rupam*. It has not so far been properly edited in *Epigraphia Indica* or any other special journal on inscriptions along with the rubbing¹⁹. An attempt was made by the present writer with the help of a photograph supplied by the British museum, and the key phrase *Jinānāmtrayīmambām* "the triad of the Jina's (and) Ambā" (in the accusative) in the fourth foot of the verse, as well as the correct forms of the names of the sculptor and his father in the prose passage, could be detected. Still, the entire second foot and the rest of the fourth foot (both occurring on the right of the cleft in the stone, the part that has greatly suffered weathering) proved to be elusive. A request was made to Prof. H. C. Bhayani of Ahmedabad for help; the following reading is Prof. Bhayani's, and is presented here with his gracious consent;

(a) Original text

1. 1. Om // Śrīmadbhojanarendrachandranagarīvidyādhārīmandhīḥ yo sā
tāma-resāśāsītapure prasthāpatā
1. 2. yāṃpsarāḥ vāgdevī prathamam vidhāya janānīm paśchā(?)jjinānām
trayīmambām (n)i-phalā(?)dhikām vararu(?)chimmūrtīm(?)subhām ni-
1. 3. rmmame iti subham // Sutradhāramahirasutamāṇathaleṇa ghaṭītam //
vi-tika sivadevena likhitamiti //
1. 4. Samvat 10091.

(b) Corrected and metrically arranged text

Om // Śrīmadbhojanarendrachandranagarīvidyādhārīm man[da]dhī-
ryo'sau tāma(ma)reśāśāsītapure prasthāpitā yā'psarāḥ /
Vāgdevīm prathamam vidhāya janānīm paśchājjinānām trayi-
mambām (nitya)phalādhikām vararuchīm mūrtīm śubhām nirmame//

(c) Translation

Om ! Having first fashioned the Vidyādhari of the city of the illustrious and shining Emperor Bhoja, (as also) Mother Sarasvatī which was installed in the city ruled by Amareśa (that is, Amareśvara), he who is of humble talent (that is, Maṇathala) fashioned thereafter the triad of the Jinas (and) the auspicious image of Ambā that has great brilliance and bestows fortunes evermore. Blessings. Fashioned by Maṇathala, son of the sculptor Mahira, and inscribed by the scribe (?) Śivadeva in Saṃvat 1091.

The inscription has still not been finally deciphered (and will perhaps never be, as some characters have been obliterated because of the fissure); some phrases, such as *amareśaśāsita-pura* and *nityaphalādhikā* have an element of conjecture ; the grammar seems to be faulty (while the other divinities are in the accusative, the phrase *yā'psarāḥ* is in the nominative).

.It is nonetheless clear that Bhayani's reading is a great improvement over all the previous interpretations : *-mandhīḥ* of the original makes no sense, but *mandadhīḥ* " of little talent ", as emended, qualifies the sculptor (Maṇathala) who thus speaks of himself in humble terms. The second foot of the verse, which has been the most intractable so far, has for the first time been read ; *amareśaśāsita-pura* " the city ruled by Amareśa ", if this emendation is accepted, is without doubt the present-day Onkar Mandhata in East Nimar district of Madhya Pradesh, one of the twelve *vyotirliṅgas*, which is mentioned in several other Paramāra records besides our own, and which still preserves an eleventh century temple of Amareśvara²⁰. The third *charaṇa* mentions a *trayī*, or *trīr̥thi* as it is commonly known to us, a group of three Tirthankaras, which was fashioned along with the present image of Ambā by the same sculptor, after (*paśchāt*) he had made the image of the *vidyādhari*, (*apsaras*) and Vāgdevī-Sarasvatī. The proposed reading of the text thus gives a connected account of the record; it explains the mention both of Brahmanical and Jaina deities; it shows beyond doubt that the king Bhoja is only mentioned in the verse as the ruling king and not as the donor; but, above all, it authenticates the identification of the goddess with the Jaina yakṣī Ambikā.

Though Bhoja like the other kings of his line was a Saiva, still he patronised many Jaina monks and scholars, and we may conclude this paper by naming a few of the more prominent. Nayanandi wrote the poem *Sudarśanachurita* while residing in the Jinavara-vihāra at Dhārā under Bhoja's patronage. The *purāṇasāra* was composed by Śrīchandra under the

patronage of the same king who also honoured another *āchārya* Prabhāchandra, and it was his curiosity that led Dhanapāla to write the *Tilak-amañjarī*.

Foot-Notes

- 1 It is believed that the sculpture was found in the Bhojaśālā also known as the Kamal Maula mosque. However, I cannot cite any authority on this or on the exact date when it reached the British Museum. Mr. Wladimir Zwalf, Keeper of the Indian and Oriental Antiquities of the museum writes in a personal letter : "there is no certain information about the source of this sculpture. While it is believed that it may have entered the British Museum collection from the India Museum in 1880 this is not documented..." I am grateful to Mr. Zwalf for this information; the photographs published here were supplied by the British Museum for which I must record my thanks
- 2 *Rupam* No. 17 (January 1942), pp. 1-2.
- 3 The *Sarasvatīkañihābharāṇa*, the *Syṅgārāprakāśa*, the *Syṅgāramañjarī-kāthā* the *Samarāṅgaṇasūtradhāra* are among the more important works credited to this king. The college (figuratively speaking the temple of Sarasvatī) is also referred to as the Śāradāsadma and Bhāratībhavana : S. K. Dikshit, ed; *Pārijā-tamañjarī alias Vijayaśrī by Madana* (Bhopal 1963), p. 2. It was desecrated by Muhammad Shah Khalji of Malwa in 1457 A.D.
- 4 The plump features of this adolescent boy led Gangoly to think that it was a female figure, namely the goddess Pārvatī on her lion, a belief that has never been questioned.
- 5 Gangoly suggested it was the donor; others seem to think that it is an ascetic figure.
- 6 It is impossible to identify this person. It is tempting to think that it represents the sculptor- *sūtradhāra* with his measuring rod but then the crown would not be accounted for. For the same reason it cannot be the Jaina monk who, according to legend, visited Ambikā for alms. (In brief the legend relates that Ambikā was originally the wife of a Brāhmaṇa who offered to a wandering Jaina monk the food meant for a *śrāddha*, was driven out of her house, died by jumping into a well, and was reborn as a yakshī.) We can only point out that similar bearded and worshipful figures occur also in other panels : in cave 33 Jagannāthasabhā at Ellora (A. Ghosh, ed., *Jaina Art and Architecture* I, New Delhi 1974, Pl. 122) and an unpublished sculpture, No. 0034 from Karitalai in Jabalpur district preserved in the Raipur Museum.
- 7 Ghosh, ed., *Jaina Art and Architecture* III (New Delhi 1975), Pls. 318, 343 and Pls. 324, 344.
- 8 The smaller boy is Priyāṅkara and his brother is Śubhāṅkara. Such an image is illustrated in U. P. Shah, *Jaina Bronzes - A Brief Survey*, in U.P. Shah and M. A. Dhaky, ed. *Aspects of Jaina Art and Architecture* (Ahmedabad 1975), Pl. 68.
- 9 For a goad and noose : *Rūpamañjana* VI. 19 (U. M. Sankhyatirtha, ed. *Devatā-mūrtiprakaraṇa and Rupamañjana*. U.P. Shah, 'Iconography of the Jaina Goddess Ambikā', *Journal of the University of Bombay* (N. S.) IX/2 (September 1940), pp. 158-159, cites *Trishashīśalākāpurushacharita* VIII.9 which gives a similar

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 5

Fig. 4

Fig. 3

देवगढ के मंदिर ११ के मानस्तंभ की
रोहिणीमूर्ति (१०५९ ई.) देखिये पृष्ठ २५

description. His fig. 22 illustrates an image of 1477 A.D. which follows this account.

- 10 Shah, "Jaina Bronzes", Pls 67, 68.
- 11 P. Pal, *The Sensuous Immortals* (Los Angeles, N.d.) Pl. 20; U P. Shah. *Akota Bronzes* (Bombay 1959), Pls. 14, 48b etc
- 12 The sculpture from Hinglajgarh has not been published; for the bronze in the National Museum see Ghosh, III. Pl. 343 B.
- 13 Scholarly opinion, however, has always assumed that the British Museum sculpture represents the Brahmanical Sarasvatī.
- 14 Guide to the Archaeological Museum in Gwalior (Gwalior, N.d.), Pl. XII b; two unpublished sculptures from Hinglajgarh in the Indore Museum: N.K. Bhattasali, *Iconography of Buddhist and Brahmanical Sculptures in the Dacca Museum* (reprinted New Delhi 1972), Pl. LXIII.
- 15 One of the two Pallu sculptures is published in Gosh, III, Pl. 337.
- 16 For instance T.A. Gopinath Rao, *Elements of Hindu Iconography* 1/2 (reprinted Delhi 1968), Pl. CXV from Bagali in Karnataka.
- 17 Haridas Bhattacharyya, "Sarasvati the Goddess of learning", in *Commemorative Essays Presented to Professor K. B. Pathak* (Poona 1934), p. 50.
- 18 Vincent Smith, *The Jaina Stupa and other Antiquities of Mathura* (reprinted Varanasi 1969), Pl. XCIX.
- 19 A. C. Mittal, *The Inscriptions of Imperial Paramāras* (Ahmedabad. 1979), pp. 69-70, lists these attempts, to which add Dikshit, p. xiv, fn. 1.
- 20 Mittal, Index s. v. for inscripotional references.

LIST OF FIGURES

1. So-called Vāgdevī (properly, yakshī Ambikā) in the British Museum. V. S. 1091 or 1034-35 A. D.
2. Detail showing the elephant goad in Ambikā's hand.
3. Detail of the figures on Ambikā's left.
4. Detail of the figures on Ambikā's right.
5. The pedestal inscription.

SAMBODHI

(QUARTERLY)

VOL. 9

APRIL 1980 - JANUARY 1981

Nos. 1-4

EDITORS

DALSUKH MALVANIA

DR. H. C. BHAYANI

NAGIN J. SHAH

L. D. INSTITUTE OF INDOLOGY AHMEDABAD-9

CONTENTS

	<i>Page</i>
Haribhadra's Synthesis of Yoga Shantilal M. Desai	1
The Buddhist and Jaina Concepts of Man and Society as Revealed in Their Religious Literature Padmanabh S. Jaini	40
Haoma as a Plant in The Avestan Text S. N. Ghosal	52
The Main Features of Mahāvīra's Contributions Suzuko Ohira	56
A Note on Āyāraṅga-Sutta 1.2.6.3 Michihiko Yajima	69
Uttarajjhayāna and Socio-Religious Formalism Ram Prakash Poddar	76
Ājñāpatra and Sanskrit Works on Polity—A Comparison Ganesh Thite	85
Some Special Aspects of Jaina Philosophy as a School of Indian Philosophy Arvind Sharma	92
A Paramāra Sculpture in the British Museum : Vāgdevī or Yakshī Ambikā ? Kirit Mankodi	96

